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UNMANNED AERIAL SYSTEMS IN INTERNATIONAL AVIATION LAW

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DECLARATION

This work has not previously been accepted in substance for any degree and is not being concurrently submitted in candidature for any degree.

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Abstract

This thesis is determined to research the international legal regulatory basis of unmanned aerial systems in the context of international aviation law, contemporary regulatory framework challenges, current and potential drone role in social, In the political and economic fields of human activity. Research is focused on modern challenges, opportunities, and perspectives of UAS integration and development of both regional and global normative systems concerning interactions between unmanned aviation and legal institutions. Special attention will be dedicated to both private and public sectors of drone applications in civilian and military areas, including the aspects of private-governmental cooperation and double use of technologies. The research will rely on examination of current trends in UAV's progress, its benefits, and potential risks, especially when it comes to combat converting of civil models and the unregulated proliferation of military technologies into war zones or sanctioned areas. Based on conducted study potential means of law harmonization will be proposed for sustainable development of unmanned technologies and global cooperation in correspondence with legal principles. One of the main aims is to critically analyze current legal issues concerning loopholes in the regulations and dedicate discovered outcomes to form a set of potentially applicable solutions to optimize the control mechanisms and, at the same time, avoid unnecessary complications for technical progress in this area of the global aerospace industry. The research methodology will use comparative analysis, case studies, systematic approach and legal analysis of international conventions, after conducting the research potential study areas will be determined, as well as perspective way of international cooperation for the optimization of current international aerial law frameworks.

Table of Content

Abstract.....

Introduction.....

Chapter 1: Unmanned Aerial Systems: Concept and

Development.....

1.1 Definition and Classification of UAS.....

1.2 Technological Advancements.....

1.3 Growth of UAS in Aviation.....

Chapter 2: International Aviation Law Framework and Status of

Drones.....

2.1 Challenges of UAS legal regulations.....

2.2 ICAO's Role and Standards.....

2.3 Regulations of military UAV applications

Chapter 3: Case Studies.....

3.1 Selected Case Studies of UAS Incidents.....

3.2 Comparative Analysis of National Regulatory

Approaches.....

Chapter 4: Future of UAS in International Aviation Law

4.1 Potential recommendations.....

4.2 Proposals for Legal Reform.....

4.3 Future Areas of Research.....

Conclusion.....

Reference List.....

Introduction

In the contemporary rapidly developing world global transport and communication systems became integral elements of international interactions, undoubtedly, aviation - the most modern type of transport, which traces its history since the first flight of the Wright Brothers in 1903 (NASA, 2008), and yet one of the most significant means of transportation holding a 33% share of the world cargo trade by value reaching USD 8 trillion worth of 240 billion cargo tonnes kilometers (CTK) according to International Air Transport Association data (IATA) and 2.3 billion passengers worldwide (ICAO, 2021) that provide humanity with irreplaceable logistics tools with great growth and development potential to achieve a result of 16 billion passengers carried by air transport in 2050 (IATA, 2011). Since the establishment of the Convention on International Civil Aviation also known as the Chicago Convention in 1944 (Convention on International Civil Aviation, 1944) and its coming into force in 1947 with the creation of the International Civil Aviation Organization (History: Foundation of the International Civil Aviation Organization, by ICAO) the ICAO was the main international body for coordination, regulation, and planning of the global air transport system development. And even taking into consideration the fact that new updates are still being adopted by ICAO as of 2024 (ICAO, 2024), the main ideas, concepts and provisions regarding civil piloted aviation remain stable and settled on the foundation of existing regulatory frameworks. With fast and dynamic development of research, technologies, and innovations many great new advances and achievements appear, which are still however followed by challenges, especially when it comes to effective solutions in regulation, *«Technology Advances Faster Than The Law And We Need To Have Clearer Rules» (Gabriel Sánchez, 2024)*. One of the most recently emerged and fastest growing sector of aviation are UAS - Unmanned Aerial Systems, drone the market is projected to grow up to roughly 3 times in the next half-decade: *«The global Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) market size was valued at USD 27.43 billion in 2022 and is projected to grow from USD 31.70 billion in 2023 to USD 91.23 billion by 2030» (Fortune Business Insights, 2022)*, to understand this scale in more detail, that would mean, that *«The number of UAS produced is forecasted to grow from 2 million units in 2021 to 6.5 million in 2030.» (ICAO, 2021)*. However, unlike, for example, passenger aviation vehicles, even primarily designated for civilian purposes models of drones can find their applications in dual-use and military purposes. So far, the brightest example of such technology adaptive transformation is so-called FPV (first person view) drones,

originally created for entertainment tasks, such as races, filming and indoor activities were conversed into guided loitering munitions, also known as «kamikaze drones», becoming one of the most common and yet influential weapons in the hands of the Ukrainian Defence Forces in their brave fight against full-scale Russian aggression since 2022, and even though the Ukrainian army began operating unmanned systems even earlier in 2014 against Russian regular military formations and proxy units in Donetsk and Luhansk regions (*Digital Forensic Research Lab, 2017*), we can now state that this technology reached a «peak» on the battlefield. As of 2024 «Ukraine's drone units are inflicting 80% of the frontline casualties on Russia» (*Tom Porter, 2024*). And while this desperate solution of Ukrainian defenders was at first motivated by the necessity of homeland protection, the formal reason for such technological know-how appearance in the warfare zone is not just the lack of conventional ammunition, but also simplicity and accessibility of components and equipment for this type of military UAV production. Unfortunately, this case already set a notorious precedent for worldwide combat systems evolution. There are already recorded cases of improvised armed drone usage in almost all the continents across the world: in Latin America «Mexican drug cartels plan attacks on Border Patrol agents with kamikaze drones and other explosives to fight US crackdown» (*Jennie Taer and Jorge Fitz-Gibbon, 2024*), in Africa «The use of drones by the CSP rebels, if it were to increase, could change the contours of the war between the Malian army, its Wagner auxiliaries, and the CSP rebels.» (*Christopher Betts, 2024*), and Asia «Insurgents from the Myanmar National Democratic Alliance Army (MNDAA) and government forces have started using FPV drones». As we can see, those highlights are just the «tip of the iceberg» of global unregulated dual-use UAV technology proliferation challenge, and as any other global challenge requires international cooperation, solidarity and collaboration to develop effective solutions for the harmonization of already existing and developing future International Aviation Law regulations on Unmanned Aerial Systems. Despite the risks, potential beneficial output for the economy, logistics, agriculture and other sectors of human activity may and should outweigh all of the challenges, for the sake of complex and efficient scaling of new aviation industry rise and balanced legal coverage. Even dual-use UAVs, such as Turkish Bayraktar TB2 is used in humanitarian missions, such as search & rescue operations in the Republic of Poland (*Newsroom, 2024*), some sources like World Food Program even believes that agricultural drones can play an important role at

the end of global hunger (Vornic, 2017) and in the European Union's first drone cargo airline begins its operations, which «can make air freight cheaper and remote areas more connected» (Cassauwers, 2024). Those examples once again proves, that UAVs shouldn't be just strictly limited, but instead supported by common international legal frameworks based on consensual principles, which will help this aviation area to thrive safely and prosperously.

This research thesis aims to analyze the current landscape of unmanned aerial systems as a concept in the international aviation law perspective, study practical cases and conduct a comparative analysis of different approaches and solutions in national regulatory models worldwide, define the main challenges concerning UAS's to form a vision of potential future recommendations for measures, that can assist in the effective integration of new technologies into accustomed to international legal architecture. The purpose of the presented work is to ensure safe, effective, and balanced development of unmanned aerial technologies in both economic and legal fields.

Chapter 1: Unmanned Aerial Systems: Concept and Development

1.1 Definition and Classification of UAS

To develop a comprehensive and complex understanding of UAS concept and possible issues that may concern drones, it is indeed necessary and important to clarify and distinguish aspects of terminology related to this type of aerial vehicles. Prototypes of unmanned aircraft were developed in the years of the First World War in the British Empire, in March of 1917, the first British radio-controlled aerial target was successfully tested, at the time it was not named UAV/UAS/Drone yet, and even despite promising results it was never mass-produced and used during the years of World War I. The first reference to the term «drone» is dated by the year 1935, when another unmanned aerial target developed from DH.82B Queen Bee plane was released (according to «A Brief History of Drones», by Imperial War Museum), such naming was chosen in connection to the original model of the

«Queen Bee» name, in the English language term «drone has referred to a male honeybee whose only role is to mate with the queen. Because drones, unlike worker bees, need not worry about gathering nectar or pollen, they have often been seen as idlers, who die after completion of their «mission»

(Zimmer, 2013). In the official documentation, such as the Convention on International Civil Aviation, the UAV's are defined in the next formulation: «The Global Air Traffic Management Operational Concept (Doc 9854) states and quotes: *«An unmanned aerial vehicle is a pilotless aircraft, in the sense of Article 8 of the Convention on International Civil Aviation, which is flown without a pilot-in-command on-board and is either remotely or fully controlled from another place (ground, another aircraft, space) or programmed and fully autonomous»*, this understanding of UAVs was endorsed by the 35th Session of the ICAO Assembly». (ICAO Circular 328-AN/190). And while ICAO and other regional civil institutions, such as the European Union Aviation Safety Agency, also known as EASA, share quite common visions of definitions, that correlate: *«Unmanned Aircraft means any aircraft operating or designed to operate autonomously or to be piloted remotely without a pilot on board»* (EASA, 2020). While, for example, the Arms Transfer Treaty, commonly referred to as ATT, does not specify, that so-called «drones» are exceptionally aerial platforms, and yet separate UAVs into surveillance and weaponized types: «Unmanned fixed-wing or variable-geometry wing aircraft, designed, equipped, or modified to engage targets by employing guided missiles, unguided rockets, bombs, guns, cannons or other weapons of destruction.», under this definition UAVs are covered by IV category of Conventional Weapons - Combat aircraft and unmanned combat aerial vehicles, including fixed-wing and other types of aerial platforms capable of carrying weaponry. (Stohl and Dick, 2018). So, to finalize and summarize the glossary issue, the «Max Planck Encyclopedias of International The law» provides quite a consensual and comprehensive definition for Unmanned Aerial Systems: «An unmanned aerial vehicle ('UAV') is an aircraft without a the human operator on board and is commonly referred to as a 'drone', but also as a remotely piloted vehicle ('RPV'), remotely piloted aircraft ('RPA'), remotely operated aircraft ('ROA') or, in the case of UAVs with specific combat roles, as an unmanned aerial combat vehicle ('UACV') (see also Air Warfare). In

contradistinction to conventional aircraft, UAVs are controlled either remotely by human operators or are guided by a computer program with various levels of automation and autonomy. Among UAVs» (Wagner, 2014). Since mentioned determination appears to indicate key complex aspects of the research topic, it will play the role of terminological cornerstone for this paper.

When it comes to classification, it is crucial to mention several main approaches: North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO), unlike ICAO and EASA, differentiate UAVs by autonomy level, highlighting gradation from level 0 - 100% manual controlled drone, to level 5 - fully autonomous, most likely AI-driven (Haider, 2021). However, in most cases, autonomy is not the main differentiation criteria, unlike sizes, attitudes, and ranges of flight, which are most common criteria of «NATO UAS CLASSIFICATION», which divide unmanned aerial systems into 3 classes: I class includes all of the UAS's seized less than 150 kg and range up to 50 km on 5,000 ft height of flight, it consists of 3 categories (micro, mini, and small), are applied at the squad-battalion level; II class is scaled from 150 to 600 kg, 200 km link range, and a flight ceiling of up to 16,000 ft, such UAS are dedicated for usage in brigade formations; III class is the largest and includes categories of MALE (Middle Attitude Long Endurance), HALE (High Attitude Long Endurance), and strategic strike drones (such as, for example, MQ-9 Reaper), those UASs are seized 600+ kg, and their flight calling ranges from 45,000 to 65,000 ft, the communication link range maybe unlimited, due to the satellite channel usage, this type of drone is used On the strategic level of Joint Task Forces (Szabolsci, 2016). In rare circumstances, the classification by rotor specifications may be applied, in that system drones could be sorted into single-rotor (helicopter type), multi-rotor multi-copters including director, trimotor, quadrotor, and hexacopter), fixed wing (normal wing the scheme swept back or forward wings, and the delta wing scheme) and hybrid (possessing characteristics of various categories) (Wilfried and Avoni, 2023). For more clarity and simplification, the paper will refer to standard NATO classification due to its universality and most shared recognition among the 32 NATO members and dozens of other states operating UAVs produced in

NATO countries.

Based on the provided data on standards, UAS can be referred to as remotely piloted or fully autonomous aerial vehicle, which may be equipped with all types of propulsion systems and payload, including full-scale conventional armaments, leading to drones transfer into combat aircraft sections of international regulatory treaties.

1.2 Technological Advancements

Through the past few decades, UAS has made severe advancements in terms of innovations, efficiency, and performance, and as it often occurs, the vast majority of innovations come to our lives from primarily the defense sector. Perhaps, one of the brightest examples is the MQ-1 drone produced by the United States «General Atomics», which developed from a makeshift solution called «Amber». In the 80-s years of the past century Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency - DARPA granted a garage-based company called «Leading

Systems Inc.», founded by American-Israeli engineer Abraham Karem, who would later be called the «father of drones» in the USA (Elshani, 2024) a contract for the development of medium-range tactical surveillance UAV, Karem came up with his «Amber» platform, which was at the time capable of carrying only 63 kg of payload, but demonstrated promising results in an operational range of 2200 km and 38 hours of autonomous flight, unfortunately, even despite the interest from the US NAVY the budget was cut and «LSI» company went bankrupt later ending up being bought by General Atomics (Parsch, 2004). After that, General Atomics Aeronautical Systems decided to develop the project with their financing, final result formed what is currently known as mentioned earlier MQ-1 «Predator» - a high-tech mass-produced multipurpose armed air platform, which became one of the Global War on Terror's main tools and symbols (Windrem, 2013).

Yet, global tendencies deserve more attention, rather than particular examples in this context. One of the main technological advancements in unmanned aerial systems area is Beyond Visual Line Of Sight, which will later be referred to as BVLOS. The BVLOS mainly really on satellite technological solutions allows UAS not to be limited by link transmission.

Sources, such as ground control stations, these features allow drones to operate on thousands of kilometers ranges conducting their missions for dozens of hours in the sky, and while BVLOS technology was first introduced for long-term warfare missions, it has also found its implications in commercial areas, including cargo transport missions (Emitel, 2024). With the release of 5G telecommunication technology UAS BVLOS solutions were once again boosted with new horizons and promising perspectives for future implementations, for example, top telecom market players, such as Nokia, are already working on 5G empowered BVLOS flight systems for copter drones, which are «Designed for public safety agencies, smart cities, and the construction, energy, and defense sectors, the drone can fly for up to 50 minutes and cover distances of up to 30km. Built with CE-certified hardware, the drone is reliable and robust, as well as water, dust, and weather resistant.» (Antunes, 2023).

Another important and truly contributing innovative achievement of the last years is improved batteries and accumulators for drones, the energy efficiency is one of the key differential advantages of drones toward traditional piloted aircraft, improved batteries allow

UAS to perform 24/7 surveillance, rescue, disaster monitoring, and intelligence missions with its neat drones may use not only primarily lithium-ion batteries but also self-charging batteries, which could be powered in the flight through the solar panels, top-tier corporations, such as «LG» are currently developing various conceptual projects, that will allow UAS to obtain even more advantages in long-term missions, economic sustainability, and autonomy (Shendge, 2023). When mentioning the UAS autonomy it is crucial to dive into the conceits of AI-driven drone technologies, such as, for example, swarming. In a basic understanding, swarming allows drones to form independent and complex structures, where each UAS can exchange external information, retransmit the data-link stream, and control, or be controlled by other drones. Such features allow UAS not only to avoid so-called «human factor» mistakes but also to develop a completely new level of multitasking, flexibility, and agility possibilities, which wouldn't be possible to obtain with a human operator. One of the recent examples is military swarms of drones, which may theoretically be 100% resistant to all kinds of jamming in the future by being fully AI-powered without any dependencies on in-ground or satellite control systems. (Aeronautics, 2023).

The combined intersection of the mentioned 5G, AI, and energy solutions among others once again shows that unmanned aviation has enormous growth potential without strict visible limitations at the current timeframe. And the more efficient new drone platforms and features will be - the higher demand for them will be formed both in the private and public sectors.

1.3 Growth of UAS in Aviation

With growing technological development and demand the UAS's role in the aviation sector increases correspondingly. The current European sales market of unmanned aircraft is estimated to value approximately \$ 4,5 billion as of 2024, in the next ten years it is predicted to increase by more than 10 times up to \$ 45,96 billion. Such rapid dynamic of exponential growth once again underlines the level of potential and importance UAS currently holds and will multiply it shortly (*Fact.MR, 2024*). However, Europe is indeed significant, but somehow may not be the key player according to

forecast analysts. Ernst & Young researchers predict that by 2030 Indian drone manufacturing capacity may reach a potential of \$ 23 billion, not to mention the import scale. Roughly a third part of this amount is expected to be military drones and another third will flow into the export markets, this combination of factors has all chances to make India the «drone hub of the world» (Singhal, 2022).

Without a single doubt, the UAS systems themselves would include more and more new sub-types and categories in the future, for example, one of the current, promising areas of development is air taxi. It is predicted that by the year of 2050 the Urban Air Mobility market may «generate revenues of almost USD 90 billion a year, with 160,000 commercial passenger drones playing the skies» (Berger, 2020). The above-mentioned indicators once again prove that the UAS issue does not only consist of prospects, opportunities, development, and a dynamic landscape but also potential challenges for the creation of completely new legislative processes, bases, and principles for radically new aviation sectors, which before could be perceived rather as conceptual futurism. One of the main factors that must contribute to the development of this area of air technologies must certainly be not just rational, transparent, balanced, and generally accepted at the international level regulation, but also effective legislative instruments that will not simply limit the development of the unmanned aviation sector, but instead will facilitate and stimulate this process.

Chapter 2: International Aviation Law Framework and Status of Drones

2.1 Challenges of UAS legal regulations

As stated, the cornerstone of international regulation of UAVs is the

1944 Chicago Convention on International Civil Aviation, and more precisely Article 8, which requires special permission for drone flights over the territory of foreign states. The Convention does not take into account for the specific nature of autonomous systems, and this produces legal inconsistencies. For example, the definition of UAVs as aircraft is problematic since the equipment is capable of flight independent of the operator's direct control, especially where loitering UAVs or drones have lost contact with the ground and strayed off are concerned. The most evident issue is the lack of a shared classification, already addressed in this article, and contradictions in the use of force, since drone deployment in asymmetric warfare, for example, against non-state actors, can be a violation of the principle of proportionality and distinction between combatants and civilians using reconnaissance or transport drones. The lack of mechanisms for holding operators to account for algorithmic errors or faulty targeting, unfortunately, does not facilitate the task of a proportionate approach to lawful regulation of drones. States have absolute sovereignty over their airspace, according to the Paris and Chicago Conventions. However, the extensive use of UAVs renders it challenging to manage its compliance. Therefore, over the past few years, Russian drones have entered the airspace of neighboring countries at least 15 times, with repeated incursions into Romania, Poland, Latvia, and Moldova since 2022 (Associated Press, 2024), making it increasingly important to further ban and sanction military UAVs. The lack of international drone registration and identification standards, unfortunately, only contributes to the above problems. Modern international law lags behind the technological realities of UAV use. To minimize risks, it is necessary to harmonize air, humanitarian, and criminal law norms, along with strengthening the role of ICAO in developing standards. Otherwise, the continuous use of drones will be followed by eroding the basic foundations of international security.

2.2 ICAO's Role and Standards

Currently, almost none of the civil provisions is effectively directly applicable to all UAS, whether remotely piloted or autonomous. ICAO Annex 6, Part IV: Recently adopted sets standards for the international operation of Remotely Piloted Aircraft Systems, both for transport and aerial vehicles. It applies to RPAS operating under instrument flight rules in controlled airspace with the objective of equal treatment with manned aircraft. However, in practice, piloted and unmanned vehicle operations can fundamentally differ. ICAO is working on the development of international standards and recommendations for the regulation of unmanned aircraft systems, specifically remotely piloted aircraft systems - RPAS. The main document forming the ICAO policy on the issue is the "Manual on Remotely Piloted Aircraft Systems" (Doc 10019), which was adopted in 2015. ICAO aims to implement an international regulatory framework that will ensure safe, harmonized, and seamless integration of RPAS into airspace on par with manned aviation. Most importantly, the goal is to prevent increased risks to manned aircraft when RPAS are integrated into non-segregated airspace and aerodromes. For this objective, ICAO has developed standards and recommended practices - SARPs, procedures for air navigation services - PANS, and supporting manuals. Doc 10019 serves as the basis for the work of ICAO expert groups developing specific standards and procedures and is revised regularly to take account of developments in technology and operational experience with RPAS. In addition, ICAO has established Model UAS Regulations, Parts 101, 102, and 149, that Member States can use as a template to establish or complement national regulations. These regulations are supplemented by Advisory Circulars, which are used to adapt and interpret the requirements according to the category and complexity of UAS operations. Despite the enormous contribution of Doc 10019 to the elaboration of an international framework for RPAS regulation, the document has some disadvantages, i.e., the lack of a binding character, Doc 10019 is advisory, not binding, which leads to a great variety of national regulations and can create inconsistencies for operators and manufacturers, as well as obsolescence in a rapidly developing industry leads, for example, to the fact that the document, which was published in 2015, can partially lose its topicality because since then RPAS technologies and operational requirements have progressed significantly. Even though updates regularly are provided, the typical adaptation process is more sluggish than the industry develops. The paper does not properly deal with the issues of pilot and operator training, which, according to research, are

among the causes of RPAS accidents and incidents. Problems of inadequate pilot knowledge and skills remain relevant. Pilots and operators have principal responsibility for safety, while the role of regulators and manufacturers in terms of contributing to product standardization and safety is not well established. Despite the advice from ICAO, different states have different requirements for RPAS operation and safety, which could create challenges in international operations and users (SKYbrary, 2020). ICAO, through Doc 10019 and the Model Rules, plays a key role in developing an international regulatory framework for the safe integration of RPAS into airspace. The document creates underlying principles and recommendations that guide states in developing regulations. Yet rapid technological advancement and the diversity of national approaches require constant revision and refinement of standards, as well as greater attention to operator training matters and manufacturers' obligations. Only a comprehensive and flexible approach will ensure unmanned aircraft systems' safety and effectiveness at the global level.

2.3 Regulations of military UAV applications

International law in the area of military use of unmanned aerial vehicles is actively developing and lacks any particular provisions directly regulating the issue. The focal point of reference is the provisions of international humanitarian law, i.e., Geneva Conventions' provisions, providing general norms for waging armed conflicts and dealing with civilians. International humanitarian law does not prohibit the use of military UAVs per se and does not classify them as indiscriminate weapons. The use of attack drones is subject to the same rules as manned aircraft: one should identify military targets and avoid harming the civilian population. At the same time, the parties to the conflict are obliged to do everything possible to prevent collateral damage. The issue of crossing the airspace of states with military UAVs

is still a live matter. The sovereignty of a state over its airspace is welcomed in international law, and unmanned aerial vehicles taking off without approval is an encroachment upon sovereignty and international obligation. States, however, view such episodes differently due to the lack of clear-cut international laws on the military. UAVs and that is what causes diplomatic clashes. The international community is also worried about the danger of terrorist use of drones. The lack of clear norms complicates the opposition to such threats, for example, attacks on coastal installations or civilian infrastructure. Experts refer to the need to sort out international norms and measures to resist illegal UAV employment for terrorism. In 2023, there was a Black Sea international airspace incident involving a Russian aircraft and an American unmanned aerial vehicle that crashed. Russian fighters violated international law by interfering with the American unmanned aerial vehicle freedom of flight, which is against Article 87 of the The UN Convention on the Law of the Sea, provides for freedom of overflight in international airspace. Although the United States is not a signatory to the Convention, it adopts its provisions as customary international law (*Deeks, 2023*).

In addition, Russia has consistently used drones to attack civilian targets in Ukraine. One research on over 9,500 Russian UAV strikes in Kherson characterized the intentional sending of UAVs as designed to intimidate the population of civilians against the law prohibiting attacks against civilians and civilian property in Additional Protocol I of the Geneva Conventions (Article 51(2)). Russian ground forces offensives have been cited to target terrorism installment against the the civilian population abuse of a different sort, and hence qualitative

contravention of IHL. The International Criminal Court issued warrants for arrest in 2024 against senior Russian military officials for war crimes as drone and missile strikes on civilian infrastructure in Ukraine, including power plants and substations, which had inflicted unbearable civilian suffering (*Logan, 2025*). Aside from direct application, particular attention should be paid to the issue of drone trade and technology transfer because of the proliferation of armed UAVs may prove to be one of the main dangers of this decade. Iran is indeed arming Russia with attack drones, namely the Shahid-136 model, which is being used to strike Ukrainian civilian targets and infrastructure. These deliveries violate the UN Security Council Resolution 2231 (2015), and the European Union has sanctioned Iranian persons and entities involved in manufacturing and exporting these drones to Russia. France

and other member states of the UN condemn Iran's support of Russian aggression, calling on Tehran to stop all forms of assistance and violate its international obligations. Iranian drone employment in Ukraine is a violation of international law and is heating the conflict as well as injury to the civilian populace. But, regrettably, there are no set defined limits for controlling and restricting the export of potential military technologies and most importantly their components, since now the Russians have begun to manufacture Iranian drones on their own ground from imported components (*Schmidt, 2023*). Hence, the global context of military UAV regulation is characterized by the absence of particular norms, a general perception of the current provisions of international humanitarian law and a growing necessity to create exact international standards to ensure security, sovereignty and protection of civilians.

Chapter 3: Case Studies

3.1 Selected Case Studies of UAS Incidents

The following chapter will be devoted to case studies and comparative analysis since every research project must make sure that real-world examples are appropriately cited. The most notable instances of unmanned aircraft systems being used in various countries are examined. Current local and international legal concerns in the area of unmanned aerial systems are reflected in the discussion of airspace management, property rights, and drone export restriction :

1. The 2020 case of United States v. Yorgan

Arnaldo Ramos Teran Yorgan Arnaldo Ramos Teran, the defendant in this case, was found guilty of violating the national defense airspace of the United States. During Super Bowl LIV at Miami Beach, he flew a drone inside a Temporary Flight Restriction (TFR) zone. The TFR was created by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) to ensure the security of a major event. Nevertheless, Ramos Teran violated 49 U.S.C. § 46307 by intentionally operating the drone in restricted airspace without permission. The case illustrates the harsh implementation of the drone flight prohibition over protected and strategic airspace as well as the potential for criminal prosecution for infractions. (U.S. Attorney's Office, Southern District of Florida, 2020)

2. English Injunctions on Drone Flights over Private Property (2024-2025)

The High Court in England has reviewed multiple cases concerning

the clash between the rights of landowners and drone aviation regulations. In the case of *Anglo International Upholland Ltd v Wainwright*, the court issued an injunction to prohibit low-flying drones that were trespassing on private property to record the location, which was an abandoned seminary. The court invoked section 76 of the Civil Aviation Act 1982, which safeguards drone operations at a “reasonable height” from trespass claims. The court did determine, nevertheless, that low-altitude flights intended for close-up filming did not meet this standard and represented an infringement on the owner's rights and a safety concern. In *MBR Acres Ltd v Curtin*, the court consequently imposed an injunction against drone operations at heights below 100 meters over a farm where livestock were raised, considering privacy and safety issues. These decisions establish the legal limits for drone operations over private land in the UK and highlight the increasing role of the judiciary in regulating drones, considering the equilibrium between aviation and property rights. (Derham, 2025)

3. Menashe Ephraim Case (Israel, 2006)

In Israel, Menashe Ephraim, who owns a drone company, was arrested for illegally exporting drones to China without the approval of the Israeli Ministry of Defence. The situation illustrates the rigorous implementation of export restrictions on drone technology beyond the borders of the United States. Israeli officials are worried about the spread of military and dual-use drones, especially to sites of strategic significance. The situation underscores the importance of global regulations for the sale of advanced weaponry and unmanned vehicles. (Gettinger, 2016)

4. Cyber Technology Incident (Australia, 2014)

An Australian firm, Cyber Technology, faced legal action for trying to export recreational drones without the required permits.

The attempted export of the drones, categorized as “defense and

strategic equipment” violated Australian export control regulations.

Consequently, the firm had to relinquish around AUD\$80,000 worth of drones and received a suspended sentence of 12 months. This situation highlights the severity and strictness of Australian drone export rules and underscores the importance of adhering to all protocols when exporting drones abroad. These instances illustrate various dominant patterns in global UAV regulation, such as airspace security, as the US and other nations establish and rigorously enforce temporary no-fly zones to safeguard public events and ensure national security (Cowan, 2014). Breach of these restrictions may lead to criminal charges. In the UK, courts are progressively limiting drone flights over private land, particularly in cases involving invasion, privacy, or security concerns.

Israel and Australia illustrate that exports of drones, particularly for military or dual-use purposes are heavily regulated to prevent the spread of technology to unreliable areas and nations. These examples show that international and national laws are quickly developing to regulate the use of unmanned aircraft systems safely and effectively, balancing innovation, safety, and human rights.

3.2 Comparative Analysis of National Regulatory Approaches

In the past decades, unmanned aerial vehicles have evolved into an essential part of a wide range of fields of activity, from military operations to logistics, environmental monitoring, and entertainment. Rapid deployment and diffusion have raised a chain of issues for governments and intergovernmental organizations in terms of security, privacy, legal regulation, and ethics. As the United States and the European Union are among the main players in the development and use of UAVs, their regulatory policies regarding unmanned aircraft can significantly vary. The regulation of unmanned aircraft is a multilateral practice with several different factors at play: Regulation for certification, flight restrictions, requirements of operators, protection of information issues, and responsibility for any incident that may occur. Within the EU, it is

managed by the European Aviation Safety Agency and the European Parliament. Within the USA, the Federal Aviation Administration is the main regulator of this activity, and in 2006 created the guidelines for the integration of UAVs into domestic airspace (FAA, 2006). While both the USA and the EU share a common goal of ensuring the safe and efficient use of drones, both have different approaches to regulation. While more stress is placed on integrating UAVs into the national air traffic system for the USA, more significance is attached to harmonizing regulation across the member states of the EU and making it conform to common standards of safety. For example, the European Parliament in its report "Unmanned Aircraft Systems Integration into European airspace and operation over populated areas" identifies the need for a transparent legal framework for the operation of drones in above-populated areas and their integration into airspace safely (European Parliament, 2023). One of the most prominent differences between the policies of the USA and the EU is how they view using drones for business. In the USA, companies that wish to use UAVs for delivery or other business endeavors must comply with strict standards that the FAA lays out. As the document "U.S. Drone Laws" published in 2019, require drone pilots to obtain special permits and become certified, which can hinder the speed of new technology adoption (911 Security, 2019). At the same time, in Europe, a more liberal approach is implemented, aimed at the gradual development of legislation to adapt to market needs. Security and protection of personal data are also crucial. The use of drones for information collection, namely by photography and video, raises privacy issues against citizens. Privacy is governed both at the state and federal levels in the United States. The majority of states have legislation prohibiting the use of drones to spy on an individual without their consent. Within the EU, this issue is regulated by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which puts strict boundaries on information processing obtained through drones (Lee, Hessb & Heldeweg, 2022). The US and Europe also have different Approaches to using UAVs for military purposes. The US armed forces widely utilize drones for reconnaissance and attack operations, which is controversial from an international law viewpoint. In the study "Use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles for Combat Purposes: Selected Legal and Medical Aspects", the legality of the deployment of drones for combat purposes is still a topic of debate, particularly in

armed conflicts and protecting civilians (Konaszczuk & Nogalski, 2024). Meanwhile, in Europe, the use of drones for the military is further controlled by global norms and limitations, although the recent conflict, such as that in Ukraine, is forcing an examination of such strategies. There are also substantial differences in the strategies for UAV pilot certification. In the US, commercial drone pilots must be licensed under Part 107, which requires them to pass a specific test. In Europe, the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) has established three types of UAV usage: open, special, and certified, enabling a more adaptive licensing policy based on flight risks ((European Parliament, 2023). Hence, the regulation of unmanned aviation by the USA and EU is quite similar overall but significantly different in details. The USA mainly focuses on stringent regulation of drone use for both military and commercial purposes, while the EU seeks harmonization of the regulations and gradual adaptation to technology. At the same time, security, privacy, and military application-related issues for UAVs remain a concern for the US as well as the EU. As mentioned, in unmanned aviation, legal regulation is crucial because it is what gives the framework for technology to be utilized safely. In the United States, the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) dictates standards, which regulate the use of drones in the commercial and civil sectors. One of the most significant documents is the "Unmanned Aircraft Operations in the National Airspace Systems" (FAA, 2006), which laid the foundation for UAVs being introduced into national airspace. In the European Union, the principal regulator is the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA). The European Parliament also plays an important role, intervening to coordinate legislative action and enacting legislation related to the flight of drones (European Parliament, 2023). Harmonized regulations for all member states were introduced in 2021 in the EU, dividing drones into three categories according to the level of risk of their operation. One of the distinctions between the US and the EU is that US legislation is more focused on integrating drones into air traffic with manned vehicles. The European Union, on the other hand, is more focused on having harmonized legislation across all member states and implementing harmonized safety standards for flying drones in cities. The US and EU licensing regimes differ significantly, while in the US, the law requires any drone pilot used for business purposes to be certified

with Part 107, which involves taking an exam on airspace and regulations on safety (911 Security, 2019). In the European Union, the levels of accessing operations of drones are three, however. On an open type of drone, a permit is not required but one must access online training. To operate under a special class of drone, a permit needs to be sought from a national aviation body, while with the certification, one must satisfy the same qualification requirements as any pilot of non-recreational aviation (European Parliament, 2023). One of the issues that both the US and the EU are working to address is the issue of remote identification of operators. In the US, the FAA requires all drones with a weight greater than 250 grams to be remotely identified, allowing government agencies to track them in real time. The EU is also rolling out a similar system step by step, adapting the requirements to different classes of drones. Drones pose a potential threat to civilian aviation, and that forces governments to put severe limits on flights in certain areas. In the US, laws do not allow drones in airports, government offices, and military bases. Even the launchers are prohibited from sending drones over public sites without prior authorization (911 Security, 2019). The European Union likewise possesses identical regulations but a more advanced system of designating flight zones. Some member states, such as Germany and France, impose additional restrictions on UAV operation in protected areas and near historic sites (Lee, Hessb & Heldeweg, 2022). The other important issue is the issue of flight altitude. In the United States, the maximum altitude of a civilian drone is limited to 400 feet or approximately 120 meters. Europe also has a limit, although on some occasions national aviation authorities can permit flights at higher altitudes. One of the most pressing concerns regarding UAV proliferation is the possibility of invading citizens' privacy. UAVs can be used in illegal data collection, video recording without consent, and other human rights violations. In the United States, privacy laws are state-based. For example, Texas and California criminalize using drones to monitor private property without the owner's permission (911 Security, 2019). In Europe, there The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) controls the protection of personal data and places stringent restrictions on the storage and processing of data collected with drones. The person operating the drone to collect personal data is required to obtain the consent of the individual or have a reasonable ground for collecting such data (Lee, Hessb & Heldeweg, 2022). The US and the EU Countries differently utilize drones in the military. The US armed forces deploy drones to

perform combat and reconnaissance missions. More precisely, drones such as the MQ-9 Reaper and MQ-1 Predator have been used in military interventions in the Middle East (Konaszczuk & Nogalski, 2024). In Europe, military use of UAVs is not as wide-ranging, though recent events, such as the war in Ukraine, have seen EU countries look to reexamine their drone defense strategy. Poland, Germany, and France are beginning to invest heavily in developing their unmanned systems, and the European Union is considering more coordination along these lines (Konaszczuk & Nogalski, 2024). However, the issue of whether the deployment of combat drones is compliant with international law is still pertinent. In the majority of cases, their deployment raised concerns regarding human rights, and this has been a matter of continued debate for European policymakers (Cygańczuk & Roguski, 2023). The application of Drones are always regulated as technology changes at a fast pace. The FAA in the US is working on simplifying regulations for the commercial use of drones, which will allow companies such as UPS and Amazon to utilize drone deliveries more widely (Carr, 2022). In Europe, the European Parliament has considered whether it would be feasible to create a single digital platform to control the flights of drones in urban areas that would more effectively allow them to control their movement (European Parliament, 2023). It is to be hoped that over the next few years, the EU and the US will be forced to collaborate even more tightly on regulation in an attempt to maintain order in international air space and set mutually acceptable safety standards. But in the context of recent political events, policies and actions by Washington are becoming increasingly difficult to interpret and predict.

The development of drones in the United States and the European Union illustrates the complexity of governing emerging technology in the context of national security, commercial use, privacy, and international law. While both share the goal of enabling the safe and efficient incorporation of drones into airspace, regulation strategies are radically different. The main difference is that the United States seeks to integrate UAVs into the air traffic system along with manned aircraft, while the EU is concerned with harmonizing regulation throughout member states and attaining similar safety standards. The U.S. Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) has been issuing definitive guidance on using drones since 2006, such as certification procedures, flight altitude limits, and areas where flight is forbidden. As a

result, the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) has set three categories of UAV use – from least risky operations to certified flight, which must adhere to the same rules as traditional aviation. The largest differences between the US and the EU lie in the business sector. Commercial drone pilots in the United States require a Part 107 license, which requires them to pass an exam and meet some standards of safety. This can hold back the rapid use of drones in new areas, such as the delivery of parcels or the monitoring of crops. For example, Amazon and UPS have already started testing out unmanned delivery services, but their scale is limited by current regulatory requirements (Carr, 2022). On the other hand, the EU is more liberal. Law is gradually changing as per market needs, allowing companies to integrate drones more effectively into business processes. In addition, the European Parliament is seriously considering creating a single digital platform for planning UAV flights in urban areas (European Parliament, 2023). This could very much simplify the use of drones in industries such as logistics, medicine, and public safety. A separate issue is how safety is to be weighed against the right of the people to remain private. Drones can be used in the gathering of intelligence, video surveillance, and even mass surveillance, an issue for civilians. Privacy safeguards in the USA are federally regulated and state-by-state. In Texas and California, for example, it is illegal to use drones to stalk private property without permission from an owner (911 Security, 2019). Within the EU, this issue is regulated by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) that puts strict restrictions on processing personal data obtained by drones. Drone operators who record must obtain the permission of persons whose data they capture (Lee, Hessb & Heldeweg, 2022). Despite regulation, the problem remains because the capability of UAVs for surveillance and data analysis keeps increasing. For instance, in law enforcement, drones are used to monitor public order actively, which leads to contradictions between security guarantees and the protection of civil rights. Another dimension is the utilization of UAVs for war effort purposes. The policies of the US and the EU are quite different regarding this aspect. The US uses drones extensively for combat efforts and intelligence gathering. For example, MQ-9 Reaper and MQ-1 Predators have been used steadily in numerous Middle Eastern military conflicts (Konaszczuk & Nogalski, 2024). This leads to global controversy about the legal use of strike drones and compliance with international humanitarian law. In the EU, however, it is more restricted. Although some of the member countries, such as France, Germany and

Poland, are investing a great deal in military drones, and their use is controlled by global treaties. However, the Ukrainian war has pushed European countries to reassess their defense policy, which can lead to more usage of drones in the military (Cygańczuk & Roguski, 2023). With the rapid speed of UAV technology progress, regulation will also change. Several key areas can define regulatory policies future in the US and the EU. Because drones are international, harmonized rules for their use need to be developed in the airspace of many countries. Both the EU and the US will change the law to suit companies that are willing to include drones in logistic operations. Command of military UAVs due to increasing numbers of war drones might be enhanced by signing new global conventions that will ensure their application without abuse. The use of drones will push cities to develop technology that can regulate UAV movement better and ensure they are utilized safely. Regulation of autonomous drones will become a reality, requiring individual regulations to manage their behavior in the skies. Regulation of drones in the US and European Union is a complex and multifaceted process, encompassing safety, commercial purposes, privacy protection, and military considerations. The US has stricter controls on the use of UAVs, especially in the commercial and military sectors. The EU, for its part, aims to harmonize the regulations and develop incrementally with new technology. Differing from one another, both systems have one thing in common - to enable the safe use of drones in various industries. Future legislative reforms need to take into account both the risks and the advantages that drones bring, striking a balance between innovation and responsibility.

Chapter 4: Future of UAS in International Aviation Law

4.1 Potential recommendations

As it was noted in the research, the main international regulations are often of a superficial nature and tend to respond to contemporary challenges from a reactive position, and therefore we can observe how a significant necessity of the advanced modernization of the current legal framework, which would make it possible to transform international laws and regulations so that it would be possible to proactively support and balance the development of unmanned aerial systems arise. The existing conventions were created for incredibly different realities, as UAS began to scale up and become a global phenomenon, the global system of international security and law are facing perhaps one of the most significant and important challenges and tests since last decades. Therefore, this research dedicates its mission to formulate the framework of potential recommendations, based on which, with further work, analysis, and follow-up, it will be possible to create a set of promising and constructive solutions for the future.

First of all, it is necessary to establish mandatory identification and registration within international registries, (as prescribed in Article 17 and 18 of the Chicago Convention for the national registration of all international aircraft) for all drones weighing more than 0.5 kg, which are able to carry payload. That will allow to strengthen the responsibility of state actors for the violations and non-sanctioned transfers of unmanned technologies to other regions, especially when it comes to internationally sanctioned jurisdictions and conflict zones. Accordingly, for international flights and exports, it is necessary to introduce mandatory UAS identification numbers in the ICAO Aircraft Registration Network (ARN), without exceptions, which was previously discussed in 2018 (Creamer, 2018).

It is equally important to ensure a more effective and safe integration of UAS into the international air traffic management system by implementing modern flight control and coordination technologies to prevent conflicts with manned aircraft. This could be done by requiring the mandatory installation of transponders in all UAS of NATO I class and above. This would allow for more effective regulation of the use of drones in international airspace and would impose additional responsibility on both countries and companies operating unmanned systems. Moreover, such solution would be a logical development of the US and EU "Remote ID" initiative for drones (EASA, 2023).

This practice of PPL (private pilot license) and CPL (commercial pilot license) licenses shall be effectively adapted both for civilian operators and for potential company pilots who use UAS for their operations. However, it is important to note that for the effective implementation of potential recommendations, not only a consensus among the key institutions of the countries of the democratic world required, but also a completely new mechanism of economic and political input of diversified sanctions pressure on other important drone market players that systematically ignore existing regulations, including China, Iran and Russia, which are already holding the ICAO Red Flag (Villamizar, 2022).

4.2 Proposals for Legal Reforms

While discussing potential legal reforms, it is crucial to comply with the Chicago Convention, which is a beacon for international aviation, but it would be logical to recommend making changes to Article 8 of the convention to add specific provisions for UAS, including their standardized classification and the basic principles of liability of operators, which should be accepted on the highest international levels. As follows, it is also important to improve Article 17 for the obligatory registration of UAS in national and later international registries with the transfer of data to ICAO databases. Article 19 could obtain additional rules for the safety of airways and the navigation of drones in international airspace. Harmonization of regional regulations is equally important, in addition to the Standardized European Rules of the Air (SERA), the most significant aspect is the unification of standardization of UAS classes, which, as noted, can be based on the current NATO system for separation by weight and flight range.

Parallel steps should include creation of an international working group under the auspices of ICAO, which would develop a mechanism for adopting common standards for UAS categories - civil, military and dual-purpose, since recently even the most improvised and primitive drones can turn into deadly weapons and this must be taken into account for

decision making processes. The task of the working group should not only include determination of clear operational and technical characteristics, but also development of mechanisms for international public-private consensus and compromise regarding their adoption at the highest level. And on the basis of these mechanisms, a clear strategy for reactions to future violations and threats to new rules shall be formed.

In order for sanctions, as a form of reaction, to be effective, it is necessary to introduce a centralized international database of UAS incidents under the auspices of ICAO in cooperation with other global organizations, in particular, for civil violations, Interpol could take on such a role.

The database should contain information on incidents, violations, technical failures and illegal actions concerning drones, collected from national aviation administrations and security services. To ensure transparency and improve the effectiveness of risk analysis, access to the database should be provided to participating countries and research organizations. It is also important to create a mandatory incident reporting system for operators and regulatory authorities. Usage of the data from this database will allow for regular updating and improvement of international safety regulations and standards.

4.3 Future Areas of Research

UAS is an incredibly promising and perspective aviation industry, with a high probability it will take more than one year, and possibly even a decade, before international law “catches up” to the pace of technological development and will be able to correspondently ensure the safe development of drones. Therefore, it is extremely important to encourage and support further research on this topic equally in both the technological and legal fields. Key points of future studies may be:

- Analysis of air traffic management technology for safe synergy of UAS and manned aviation.
- Research into the legal, ethical and technical sectors of the potential use of autonomous AI drone control systems, in particular aspects of responsibility and decision-making (especially in the context of national security and defense)
- Study of the social and economic outcomes of the mass distribution, adaptation and use of UAVs in a wide variety of aspects of people's lives, especially in the logistics and agricultural sectors.
- Development of methods for protecting critical facilities from aerial threats, which unfortunately have become much more relevant with the development of aerial loitering munitions, also known as "kamikaze UAV"

These vectors are determined by the current trends in the development of this field of studies and have an extremely wide potential for further expansion and deepening in both humanitarian and technological spheres.

Conclusion

UAS are rapidly transforming aviation and becoming an integral part of international transport, the conducted research demonstrates that UAS, in parallel with significant benefits for the economy, logistics, humanitarian missions and the agricultural complex, also create serious challenges for international aviation law, which is not yet able to respond quickly enough to these changes. Analysis of international and regional legal bases revealed the fragmentation of existing approaches to UAS regulation, which leads to imbalances in the classification, certification and legal support of drones, creating risks for both civilian and military aspects of UAS use. The studied cases demonstrated, on the one hand, flexibility, and

on the other, a certain chaos and superficiality of existing laws on drones, which creates a large-scale field for both further research and new precedents.

But positive examples of drone usage for humanitarian, search and rescue, environmental and commercial purposes emphasize that, despite all the risks, future actions should be aimed at creating a favorable field for the safe integration of UAS, and not just restrictions in international airspace, that deserve the priority attention of international legislators.

In particular, there is a real and significant need for:

- Strengthening ICAO in the development of new standards for drones
- Promoting international cooperation on data exchange, tracking drones and preventing the proliferation of these technologies for illegal and terrorist purposes
- Creating fundamental principles that will allow changing the legal approach from reactive to proactive

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